

Adhocracy and Clan Organizational Cultures as Determinants of Effective Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study investigated adhocracy and clan organizational cultures as determinants of effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Two (2) research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. A Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 350 principals of senior secondary schools in Rivers State, with 241 male and 109 female principals. The study sampled 350 principals from the public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A census sampling technique was utilized because of the small size of the population. The instrument used in collection of data for the study was a 10 self-structured questionnaire titled Adhocracy and Clan Organizational Cultures for Effective Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ACOCEMPSSSQ). The reliability of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach alpha, which yielded a reliability index of .892. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while an independent t-test was applied to test the null hypotheses at a significance level of .05. The findings of the study indicated that the management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was shaped by a blend of adhocracy and clan organizational cultures. Based on these findings, the study concluded that the management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is shaped by a mix of organizational cultures adhocracy and clan. These elements promote innovation, collaboration, structure, and accountability, which are crucial for improving school management and academic outcomes. Therefore, it is recommended that the principals of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State should ensure that school organizational culture are maintained to for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, principals should ensure that clan school organizational cultures are maintained to enhance effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Keywords: Adhocracy, Clan, Organizational Cultures, Determinants, Effective Management, Public, Senior, Secondary Schools, Rivers State, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

Organizational culture is a key determinant of institutional effectiveness and leadership success in both corporate and educational settings. It refers to the shared beliefs, values, assumptions, and behavioral norms that shape how members of an organization interact and work toward common goals (Schein, 2017). In the school environment, organizational culture provides a framework for guiding managerial decisions, motivating teachers, and promoting collective responsibility. Effective management in public senior secondary schools, particularly in Rivers State, Nigeria, depends not only on administrative competence but also on the prevailing cultural orientation that governs relationships and leadership practices (Ogbonna & Harris, 2000).

Among the elements of organizational culture, the Clan and Adhocracy cultures are particularly relevant for educational management because they emphasize flexibility, collaboration, and innovation, which are essential for effective school administration in dynamic environments (Alavi et al., 2006). The Clan organizational culture emphasizes teamwork, participation, shared values, and a sense of family within the organization (Denison & Mishra, 1995). It is characterized by high trust, open communication, and a supportive environment where leaders act as mentors or facilitators rather than authoritative figures (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). In schools operating under clan culture, decision-making tends to be participatory, promoting mutual respect among teachers, administrators, and students. This atmosphere enhances morale, teacher commitment, and overall job satisfaction (Lok & Crawford, 2004). Such a culture also promotes collaboration, mentorship, and emotional support, which can improve instructional quality and organizational effectiveness (Nwankwo, 2019).

Conversely, the Adhocracy organizational culture is characterized by innovation, adaptability, creativity, and risk-taking (Daft, 2016). Institutions that exhibit adhocracy traits encourage experimentation, learning from failure, and proactive responses to environmental changes (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). In educational settings, this culture type promotes the development of new teaching strategies, technological adoption, and curriculum innovations (Ezekiel, 2021). School leaders operating in an adhocracy culture tend to be visionary, entrepreneurial, and willing to empower staff to try new methods to solve educational challenges (Amzat & Valdez, 2017). This flexibility is particularly vital in Nigeria's evolving educational context, where public schools face challenges of resource inadequacy, policy inconsistencies, and the need for 21st-century teaching practices.

In Rivers State, public senior secondary schools are managed under complex socio-political and economic conditions. The success of these institutions depends largely on how principals utilize organizational culture to improve management efficiency, motivate teachers, and enhance learning outcomes (Egwurube, 2022). A clan culture can build a sense of belonging, trust, and shared vision among school personnel, while an adhocracy culture can inspire innovation and adaptability in addressing systemic issues such as inadequate infrastructure, fluctuating student enrollment, and curriculum reforms. Integrating both cultures allows school administrators to balance human relations with innovation and essential traits for sustainable school improvement (Onwuka, 2020).

Despite the importance of organizational culture, studies have shown that many school leaders in Nigeria pay limited attention to its impact on management effectiveness (Omorieg & Ihensekhien, 2021). Consequently, some schools operate under rigid bureaucratic systems that hinder teacher creativity, collaboration, and commitment. Understanding how Adhocracy and

Clan cultures contribute to effective management is thus crucial for improving administrative performance and promoting a more dynamic educational environment in Rivers State.

This study therefore investigates how adhocracy and clan organizational cultures are utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings are expected to provide insights into how cultural flexibility and collaboration can enhance leadership effectiveness, teacher motivation, and school performance.

Statement of the Problem

The effectiveness of school management in Nigeria, particularly in public senior secondary schools, has increasingly come under scrutiny due to persistent administrative inefficiencies, low teacher morale, and declining academic performance. In Rivers State, principals are expected to manage schools in ways that promote collaboration, innovation, and responsiveness to educational challenges. However, the prevailing management culture in many public schools remains rigid, bureaucratic, and hierarchical, which often limits flexibility, creativity, and shared decision-making. This situation raises concerns about the extent to which organizational culture contributes to effective school management.

Evidences suggest that adhocracy and clan organizational cultures are positively associated with innovation, teamwork, and institutional effectiveness. Yet, little is known about how these cultural orientations are utilized within the context of Nigerian public senior secondary schools, particularly in Rivers State. Many school leaders may be unaware of the strategic role organizational culture plays in shaping leadership behavior, teacher engagement, and school improvement. Consequently, the continued dominance of traditional hierarchical practices may undermine the potential for participatory management and innovative problem-solving.

Therefore, the problem of this study is to determine how adhocracy and clan organizational cultures are utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, and to what extent these cultural dimensions influence administrative efficiency, teacher motivation, and overall school performance.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate adhocracy and clan organizational cultures as determinants of effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study intend to:

- Examine how adhocracy organizational culture is utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Assess how clan organizational culture is utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- How is adhocracy organizational culture utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- How is clan organizational culture utilized for effective management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on how adhocratic organizational culture is utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on how clan organizational culture is utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Denison's Theory of Organizational Culture

Denison's Theory of Organizational Culture is one of the most influential frameworks for understanding how organizational culture influences effectiveness and performance. Developed by Daniel R. Denison in the early 1990s, the theory posits that organizational culture is a system of shared values, beliefs, and assumptions that directly affects an organization's ability to achieve its goals (Denison & Mishra, 1995). The model emphasizes that culture is not merely a set of abstract ideals but a measurable and functional aspect of organizational life that determines how individuals behave and how effectively the organization performs.

Denison's model identifies four key cultural traits that are strongly linked to organizational effectiveness: involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission (Denison, 1990). Each of these dimensions represents a critical aspect of how culture operates within an organization.

- Involvement refers to the degree to which employees at all levels are engaged, empowered, and take ownership of organizational goals. Organizations that score high in involvement tend to validate a sense of belonging and commitment among employees. This trait aligns closely with the concept of a clan culture, where teamwork, trust, and participation are emphasized (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). In educational settings, involvement translates into teacher participation in decision-making, collaborative planning, and shared leadership all of which contribute to effective school management.
- Consistency relates to the presence of core values, agreement, and coordination across the organization. Denison (1990) argues that consistent organizations possess a strong and unified identity that guides members' behavior. This dimension ensures stability and internal cohesion, enabling schools or institutions to maintain uniform standards, discipline, and cooperation among staff. Consistency, when balanced with flexibility, helps educational leaders align institutional goals with staff expectations.

- Adaptability denotes an organization's ability to respond to changes in its external environment. It involves organizational learning, innovation, and the capacity to translate external demands into internal action (Denison & Mishra, 1995). This trait reflects characteristics of adhocracy culture, where creativity, experimentation, and responsiveness to change are encouraged (Daft, 2016). In the context of public secondary schools, adaptability enables administrators and teachers to adopt new pedagogical approaches, respond to policy reforms, and integrate technology in teaching and learning.
- Mission represents the organization's sense of purpose, direction, and strategic intent. According to Denison (2000), mission provides meaning to employees' work and defines organizational goals that give coherence to decision-making. In schools, a clearly defined mission ensures that teachers and administrators understand their roles in achieving educational objectives, encourages accountability and performance improvement.

Denison's model integrates both internal and external orientations as well as stability and flexibility dimensions, providing a comprehensive framework that connects culture with performance outcomes. Empirical studies support the model's applicability across diverse sectors, showing that organizations with strong cultural traits of involvement, adaptability, consistency, and mission tend to perform better (Yilmaz & Ergun, 2008). In the educational sector, these cultural traits enhance teacher motivation, promote shared governance, and improve institutional effectiveness (Egwurube, 2022).

Denison's Theory of Organizational Culture highlights that an effective organization balances employee engagement, shared values, adaptability to change, and a clear mission. When applied to school management, the model suggests that principals who promote participatory leadership, consistency in values, adaptability to innovations, and a strong educational mission can significantly enhance school performance. Thus, Denison's framework provides a useful theoretical foundation for examining how adhocracy and clan cultures contribute to the effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Effective Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools

Effective management of public senior secondary schools is essential for achieving educational quality, organizational stability, and improved student outcomes. School management involves the systematic coordination of human, material, and financial resources to accomplish institutional goals efficiently and effectively. According to Okumbe (1998) and Ololube (2017), educational management refers to the process of designing, developing, and effecting resources in order to achieve educational objectives. In the context of public senior secondary schools, effective management requires competent leadership, strategic planning, participatory governance, accountability, and an enabling organizational culture that promotes collaboration and innovation.

The effectiveness of school management largely depends on the leadership capacity of principals. Effective school leaders play multiple roles as administrators, instructional leaders, mentors, and change agents (Bush, 2020). In public senior secondary schools, the principal's ability to articulate a clear vision, motivate staff, and ensure adherence to educational policies determines the overall performance of the school. Principals who employ participatory leadership styles tend to promote teamwork and collective responsibility among teachers and

non-teaching staff (Nwankwo, 2019). Through collaborative leadership, they build a culture of trust, accountability, and commitment that enhances school efficiency and teacher morale.

A critical aspect of effective management is strategic planning and resource utilization (Oloube, 2017). Secondary schools in Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, often face resource limitations, including inadequate infrastructure, insufficient funding, and shortage of instructional materials. Effective management entails prioritizing resources, developing strategic plans, and seeking innovative ways to mobilize support from government agencies, Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs), and community stakeholders (Egwurube, 2022). Principals who demonstrate financial prudence and transparency in resource allocation promote confidence among staff and the community, which contributes to sustainable school improvement.

Human resource management is also fundamental to effective school management. Teachers are the cornerstone of educational delivery; hence, their recruitment, motivation, and development are central to school success (Daft, 2016). Effective principals ensure that teachers are adequately supervised, supported, and provided with opportunities for professional development. According to Amzat and Valdez (2017), teacher empowerment enhances instructional quality, creativity, and job satisfaction. This can be achieved through mentorship programs, peer collaboration, and recognition of teacher achievements. When teachers are valued and involved in decision-making, their productivity and sense of ownership increase, leading to better teaching and learning outcomes.

Effective management equally depends on organizational culture, which involves the values, norms, and behaviors shared within the school environment. A positive organizational culture promotes communication, innovation, and teamwork among staff (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Schools that promote clan or adhocracy cultural traits, for example, experience greater collaboration, adaptability, and teacher commitment (Denison & Mishra, 1995). In contrast, hierarchical cultures that rely excessively on control and formal rules may hinder creativity and reduce teacher morale. Thus, an effective school manager balances structure with flexibility to create a supportive and performance-oriented culture.

Furthermore, effective management entails monitoring, evaluation, and accountability mechanisms. Regular assessment of teaching performance, student achievement, and administrative practices enables principals to identify areas for improvement. Continuous feedback and performance appraisal systems ensure that educational standards are maintained (Onwuka, 2020). In Rivers State, public schools operate under the oversight of the Ministry of Education and the Secondary Education Board, effective management requires aligning institutional practices with state policies while maintaining professional autonomy in daily operations.

Community and parental involvement also play a pivotal role in effective management. The integration of community stakeholders through PTAs, alumni associations, and local education committees helps schools mobilize additional resources, enhance student discipline, and promote accountability (Ezekiel, 2021). These types of partnerships strengthen school governance and ensure that educational programs respond to local needs and aspirations.

Thus, effective management of public senior secondary schools involves visionary leadership, strategic planning, teacher empowerment, and the cultivation of a supportive organizational culture. It requires the ability to adapt to changing educational demands while ensuring efficiency, accountability, and inclusiveness.

How Adhocracy Organizational Culture is Utilized for Effective Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools

Adhocracy organizational culture represents a dynamic and flexible approach to management that prioritizes innovation, creativity, and responsiveness to change. According to Cameron and Quinn (2011), adhocracy culture is characterized by adaptability, risk-taking, and an external orientation that focuses on environmental responsiveness and continuous improvement. In educational institutions such as public senior secondary schools, this culture enables leaders and teachers to think creatively, embrace innovation, and proactively address emerging challenges in teaching, learning, and administration. The utilization of adhocracy organizational culture in Rivers State schools can therefore enhance leadership effectiveness, promote innovation, and improve overall school performance.

The school environment in Rivers State is marked by rapid social, economic, and technological changes that demand new administrative and instructional strategies. School principals, as key managers, must adopt flexible leadership approaches that align with the dynamic nature of education in the 21st century. Adhocracy culture encourages school leaders to move away from rigid bureaucratic models and embrace participatory and innovative management practices (Daft, 2016). This cultural orientation promotes an environment where experimentation and new ideas are valued, and teachers are empowered to develop creative teaching methods that enhance learning outcomes (Ezekiel, 2021).

One of the primary ways adhocracy culture is utilized in the management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is through innovation in instructional practices. Schools that adopt adhocratic values encourage teachers to use modern technologies, develop learner-centered approaches, and implement new pedagogical models that promote critical thinking and problem-solving. Principals who practice adhocracy leadership also support teachers by providing professional development opportunities and resources that endorse innovation (Amzat & Valdez, 2017). For instance, teachers may be encouraged to design digital learning materials, experiment with blended learning strategies, or initiate student-led projects that cultivate creativity and independent thinking.

Additionally, adhocracy culture promotes collaborative problem-solving and shared leadership. In this culture type, leaders function as facilitators and innovators who encourage participation in decision-making (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Principals who adopt this approach often involve teachers in developing school improvement plans, designing extracurricular programs, and implementing reforms that address local educational needs. This participatory governance builds trust, enhances communication, and creates a sense of ownership among staff, which ultimately leads to more effective management outcomes (Nwankwo, 2019).

Another essential feature of adhocracy culture is responsiveness to environmental change. Public secondary schools in Rivers State operate within a complex system influenced by government policies, community expectations, and technological advancements. Adhocracy culture equips school administrators to adapt to these changes swiftly by encouraging organizational learning and flexibility (Denison & Mishra, 1995). For example, during curriculum reforms or shifts in national education policy, schools with adhocratic orientation are more likely to adjust their management and instructional strategies effectively. Similarly, such schools tend to respond quickly to technological changes, incorporating digital tools for record keeping, communication, and instructional delivery (Onwuka, 2020).

Furthermore, adhocracy culture enhances teacher motivation and engagement by promoting autonomy and professional growth. When teachers are given the freedom to innovate and make meaningful contributions to school improvement, their sense of belonging and commitment increases (Lok & Crawford, 2004). In Rivers State, where many public schools face challenges such as inadequate facilities and resource constraints, an adhocratic approach helps sustain morale by empowering teachers to identify creative solutions to local problems rather than waiting for directives from higher authorities (Egwurube, 2022).

However, the utilization of adhocracy culture in public senior secondary schools is not without challenges. Some school leaders may lack the training or disposition to support risk-taking and innovation, preferring traditional hierarchical structures. Additionally, systemic barriers such as limited funding, bureaucratic oversight, and policy restrictions can hinder the implementation of adhocratic practices. Nevertheless, when effectively adopted, adhocracy culture enables schools to remain flexible, future-oriented, and adaptive to the evolving demands of education in Nigeria.

On the whole, adhocracy organizational culture is utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools through innovation, participatory leadership, adaptability, and teacher empowerment. It encourages experimentation, supports collaborative decision-making, and strengthens the capacity of schools to respond to change. Promoting culture that values creativity and flexibility helps school leaders to enhance administrative effectiveness, teacher motivation and student learning outcomes. Accordingly, integrating adhocracy principles into the management of public secondary schools is essential for building resilient, progressive, and high-performing educational institutions in Rivers State.

How Clan Organizational Culture is Utilized for Effective Management of Senior Secondary Schools

Clan organizational culture represents a management orientation that emphasizes collaboration, cohesion, trust, and shared values among members of an organization. It is rooted in the notion of the organization as an extended family, where leaders act as mentors and facilitators, and employees work cooperatively toward collective goals (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). In the context of educational institutions, particularly public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, the clan culture model provides a foundation for participatory management, teacher engagement, and effective leadership. This culture type aligns with the principles of human relations and transformational leadership, which prioritize people over processes and cooperation over control.

The utilization of clan organizational culture in managing senior secondary schools in Rivers State begins with the development of a supportive and family-like atmosphere. School principals who embrace clan values promote mutual respect, open communication, and interpersonal relationships among staff. This approach enhances trust and teamwork, which are essential for achieving educational goals (Denison & Mishra, 1995). When teachers feel valued and respected, they are more motivated to perform their duties effectively and contribute to the school's success. Such a sense of belonging promotes collective responsibility, where every staff member perceives themselves as an integral part of the school's vision and mission (Lok & Crawford, 2004).

Another key way clan culture is utilized is through shared leadership and participatory decision-making. In clan-oriented schools, principals encourage teachers and other stakeholders to participate in developing school policies, improvement plans, and curricular activities

(Egwurube, 2022). This inclusive management style ensures that decisions reflect the collective wisdom of the staff, leading to higher levels of commitment and ownership. For instance, involving teachers in setting academic goals or planning extracurricular activities enhances their sense of agency and accountability. Such participatory governance reduces resistance to change, builds trust, and promotes harmony within the school community (Nwankwo, 2019).

Clan culture also supports mentorship, collaboration, and capacity building. Leaders in this environment act as mentors who guide and empower teachers to improve their skills and performance. Regular staff meetings, peer mentoring, and professional development programs serve as platforms for sharing experiences and best practices (Amzat & Valdez, 2017). In Rivers State, where some schools struggle with inadequate resources and limited access to training, this internal culture of mutual support and knowledge sharing becomes a critical tool for improving educational quality. Through mentoring, senior teachers assist less experienced colleagues, creating a collaborative learning culture that enhances professional competence and effectiveness.

Moreover, clan culture emphasizes communication and conflict resolution through dialogue. In schools characterized by this culture, communication channels are open and transparent, allowing issues to be addressed promptly before they escalate. Principals who manage through clan culture adopt a consultative approach in resolving conflicts among staff or between teachers and students (Onwuka, 2020). This approach minimizes tension, builds mutual understanding and maintains organizational stability, which are key elements for effective school management.

The clan culture also enhances teacher motivation and job satisfaction by recognizing and rewarding commitment, loyalty, and teamwork (Daft, 2016). When teachers perceive that their contributions are appreciated and their well-being matters, their intrinsic motivation increases. Such motivation translates into improved classroom performance, discipline, and student outcomes. In Rivers State, where teachers often face challenging working conditions, promoting a culture of care and support can serve as a buffer against stress and burnout, promoting retention and institutional continuity (Omoregie & Ihensekhien, 2021).

Finally, the integration of parents and community members into the school system is another manifestation of clan culture. Through the building of strong school-community relationships, principals reinforce the family-like nature of the school environment. Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) and community partnerships create avenues for resource mobilization, moral support, and shared accountability for student success (Ezekiel, 2021). This external collaboration mirrors the internal cohesion of the staff, resulting in an inclusive and effective management system.

Therefore, clan organizational culture is utilized in the effective management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State through participatory leadership, mentorship, open communication, teamwork, and community involvement. It promotes trust, loyalty, and a shared sense of purpose among teachers and administrators, leading to improved management efficiency and school performance. Schools that embrace this culture benefit from stronger collaboration, higher morale, and enhanced organizational stability. Consequently, the promotion of clan culture principles in Rivers State's education system can significantly improve the management and performance of public senior secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. This research design was considered worthy as it helped the researcher to investigate adhocracy and clan organizational cultures as determinants of effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

The study population comprised 350 principals of senior secondary schools in Rivers State, with 241 male and 109 female principals (Source: Planning, Research Statistics Department; Rivers State Senior School Board, 2024).

The study sampled 350 senior secondary school principals in Rivers State, consisting of 241 males and 109 females. Due to the relatively small size of the population, the study employed a census sampling technique, meaning that all members of the population were included in the sample. This approach ensures comprehensive representation of the entire group, eliminating the need for random sampling.

The instrument that was used for collection of data for the study was a 10 items self-structured questionnaire titled 'Adhocracy and Clan Organizational Cultures for Effective Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ACOCEMPSSSQ)'. The questionnaire consists of two sections. Section 'A' deal with the demographic data of the respondents, while section 'B' elicited the opinion of the respondents of the two (2) research questions. A 4-point likert rating scale was used, in the format of Strongly Agreed (SA) =4, Agreed (A) =3, Disagreed (D) =2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) =1.

Validation of the instrument was carried out by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts from the Department of Educational Management at Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. All recommended corrections were made before finalizing the questionnaire for distribution.

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a test-retest method was employed. Copies of the instrument were administered to 20 principals in private secondary schools in Rivers State, and after two-week interval, fresh copies of the questionnaires were re-administered to the same respondents to assess the consistency of the instrument over time. The data collected were analyzed using PPMC package, resulting in a reliability coefficient of .892, indicating a satisfactory level of internal consistency.

A total of 350 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the principals of the 350 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State by the researcher and two research assistants, who assisted with the administration and retrieval of the questionnaires. The respondents were encouraged to complete the questionnaire immediately to ensure a high return rate. Some respondents were allowed to complete the questionnaire at their convenience and were later visited for collection. Out of the 350 questionnaire distributed, while 340 were returned and used for data analysis, representing a return rate of 97.14%.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the independent t-test was employed to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for interpreting the mean scores was set at 2.50. Any mean score of 2.50 or above was considered agreed, while any score below 2.50 was considered disagreed. For hypotheses testing, the null hypothesis was accepted if the calculated t-value (t-cal) was less than the tabulated t-value (t-tab), and rejected if the t-cal value was greater than the t-tab value.

RESULTS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: How is adhocracy organizational culture utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on how adhocracy organizational culture enhance the effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

s/n	Item Statements (N=340)	Male Principals N=236		Female Principals N=104		Mean Set	SD	Decision
		Mean	SD ₁	Mean	SD ₂			
1	Adhocracy organizational culture encourages innovation and creativity among teachers and staff	2.56	.64	2.72	.68	2.64	.66	Agree
2	Adhocracy organizational culture allows schools to be flexible and adaptive to change	2.78	.70	2.55	.65	2.67	.68	Agree
3	Adhocracy organizational culture enables quick decision-making	2.60	.65	2.57	.64	2.59	.65	Agree
4	Adhocracy organizational culture promotes collaboration among teachers, administrators, and students	2.55	.64	2.63	.66	2.59	.65	Agree
5	Adhocracy organizational culture makes teachers feel empowered to take initiatives	2.60	.65	2.57	.64	2.59	.65	Agree
Grand Mean Set & Standard deviation		2.62	.66	2.61	.65	2.62	.66	Agree

Table 1 presents the mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on how adhocracy organizational culture enhances the effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis presented in the above table showed the following range perceptions for items 1 to 5: Adhocracy organizational culture encourages innovation and creativity among teachers and staff (Mean=2.64 and SD=.66), Adhocracy organizational culture allows schools to be flexible and adaptive to change (Mean=2.67 and SD=.68), Adhocracy organizational culture enables quick decision-making (Mean=2.59 and SD=.65), Adhocracy organizational culture promotes collaboration among teachers, administrators, and students (Mean=2.59 and SD=.65) and Adhocracy organizational culture makes teachers feel empowered to take initiatives (Mean=2.59 and SD=.65). These indicated that respondents generally agreed on all the items as their mean ratings exceeded the criterion of 2.50. Furthermore, the table showed a grand mean and standard deviation (Mean = 2.62 and SD = .66), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50. This further implies that, adhocracy organizational culture was utilized for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: How is clan organizational culture utilized for effective management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on how clan organizational culture enhance the effective management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State

s/n	Item Statements	(N=340)	Male Principals N=236		Female Principals N=104		Mean Set	SD	Decision
			Mean	SD ₁	Mean	SD ₂			
6	Clan organizational culture promotes a sense of belonging among teachers, students, and staff		2.65	.67	2.68	.67	2.67	.67	Agree
7	Clan organizational culture encourages teamwork and collaboration among teachers and staff members		2.61	.65	2.59	.65	2.60	.65	Agree
8	Clan organizational culture promotes mentorship programs		2.63	.66	2.63	.63	2.63	.65	Agree
9	Clan organizational culture facilitates open communication channels		2.59	.65	2.68	.67	2.64	.66	Agree
10	Clan organizational culture provides stability and continuity		2.61	.65	2.64	.66	2.63	.66	Agree
Grand Mean Set & Standard deviation			2.62	.66	2.64	.66	2.63	.66	Agree

Table 2 presents the mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on how clan organizational culture enhances the effective management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis presented in the above table showed the following range perceptions for items 6 to 10: Clan organizational culture promotes a sense of belonging among teachers, students, and staff (Mean=2.67 and SD=.67), Clan organizational culture encourages teamwork and collaboration among teachers and staff members (Mean=2.60 and SD=.65), Clan organizational culture promotes mentorship programs (Mean=2.63 and SD=.65), Clan organizational culture facilitates open communication channels (Mean=2.64 and SD=.66) and Clan organizational culture provides stability and continuity (Mean=2.63 and SD=.66). These indicated that respondents generally agreed on all the items as their mean ratings exceeded the criterion of 2.50. Furthermore, the table showed a grand mean and standard deviation (Mean = 2.63 and SD = .66), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50. This further implies that, clan organizational culture enhance the effective management of senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of adhocratic organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of adhocracy organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents'	N (340)	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	Decision
Male Principals	236	2.62	.66	338	.117	No significant
Female Principals	104	2.61	.65			

Table 3 presents the summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of adhocratic organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The result of table above shows that the t-calculated value of .117 is less than t-critical value of ± 1.96 at p-value of .05 level of significance at the degree of freedom of 338. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of adhocratic organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of clan organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of clan organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents'	N (340)	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	Decision
Male Principals	236	2.62	.66	338	-.661	No significant
Female Principals	104	2.64	.66			

Table 4 presents the summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of clan organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The result of table above shows that the t-calculated value of -.661 is less than t-critical value of ± 1.96 at p-value of 0.05 level of significance at the degree of freedom of 338. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of clan organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Adhocracy Organizational Culture for the Effective Management

The study revealed that adhocracy organizational culture enhanced the effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of adhocracy organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the view of Daft (2016) and Ezekiel (2021) who stated that adhocracy culture encourages

school leaders to move away from rigid bureaucratic models and embrace participatory and innovative management practices. The cultural orientation promotes an environment where experimentation and new ideas are valued, and teachers are empowered to develop creative teaching methods that enhance learning outcomes.

In the same vein, Amzat and Valdez (2017) found that schools that adopt adhocracy values encourage teachers to use modern technologies, develop learner-centered approaches, and implement new pedagogical models that promote critical thinking and problem-solving. Principals who practice adhocracy leadership also support teachers by providing professional development opportunities and resources that promotes innovation

Additionally, Cameron and Quinn (2011) and Nwankwo (2019) noted that adhocracy culture promotes collaborative problem-solving and shared leadership. In this culture type, leaders function as facilitators and innovators who encourage participation in decision-making. Thus, principals who adopt this approach often involve teachers in developing school improvement plans, designing extracurricular programs, and implementing reforms that address local educational needs. The participatory governance of adhocracy culture builds trust, enhances communication, and creates a sense of ownership among staff, which ultimately leads to more effective management outcomes.

Similarly, Onwuka (2020) observed that adhocracy culture equips school administrators to adapt to these changes swiftly by encouraging organizational learning and flexibility. Schools with adhocracy orientation are more likely to adjust their management and instructional strategies effectively. Likewise, such schools tend to respond quickly to technological changes, incorporating digital tools for record keeping, communication, and instructional delivery.

Clan organizational Culture for Effective Management

Data in Table 2 revealed that the respondents agreed that clan organizational culture enhances the effective management of senior secondary schools and there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the use of clan organizational culture for effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

This result is in line with Lok and Crawford (2004) who found that the utilization of clan organizational culture in managing senior secondary schools begins with the development of a supportive and family-like atmosphere, and school principals who embrace clan values promote mutual respect, open communication, and interpersonal relationships among staff.

The same is true when Egwurube (2022) found that when clan culture is utilized through shared leadership and participatory decision-making in clan-oriented schools, principals encourage teachers and other stakeholders to participate in developing school policies, improvement plans, and curricular activities. Equally, Nwankwo (2019) established that inclusive management style ensures that decisions reflect the collective wisdom of the staff, leading to higher levels of commitment and ownership. Thus, involving teachers in setting academic goals or planning extracurricular activities enhances their sense of agency and accountability. Such participatory governance reduces resistance to change, builds trust, and promotes harmony within the school community.

To Amzat and Valdez (2017), clan culture also supports mentorship, collaboration, and capacity building. Leaders in this environment act as mentors who guide and empower teachers to improve their skills and performance, through regular staff meetings, peer mentoring, and professional development programs serve as platforms for sharing experiences and best

practices. Through mentoring, senior teachers assist less experienced colleagues, creating a collaborative learning culture that enhances professional competence and effectiveness.

In Onwuka (2020) study, he found that clan culture emphasizes communication and conflict resolution through dialogue. In schools characterized by this culture, communication channels are open and transparent, allowing issues to be addressed promptly before they escalate. Principals who manage through clan culture adopt a consultative approach in resolving conflicts among staff or between teachers and students. This approach minimizes tension, builds mutual understanding and maintains organizational stability, which are key elements for effective school management. Thus, clan culture also enhances teacher motivation and job satisfaction by recognizing and rewarding commitment, loyalty, and teamwork (Daft, 2016; Omoregie & Ihensekhien, 2021).

CONCLUSION

This study has successfully investigated adhocracy and clan organizational cultures as determinants of effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The evidences remain strong that the success of school administration depends largely on the leadership competence of principals, the strategic use of resources, and the creation of an enabling organizational culture that promotes collaboration, innovation, and accountability. Principals who demonstrate participatory and transformational leadership styles promote a shared sense of purpose among teachers, students, and other stakeholders, thereby improving school effectiveness. Furthermore, the integration of supportive organizational cultures such as clan and adhocracy enhances adaptability, teamwork, and teacher motivation, which are critical for meeting contemporary educational challenges. Effective management also involves transparent resource utilization, continuous professional development, and community engagement to ensure that educational objectives align with societal needs. In Rivers State, where public schools face issues such as underfunding and infrastructural deficits, adopting innovative, culturally responsive, and collaborative management practices can significantly improve efficiency and learning outcomes. Therefore, strengthening leadership capacity and promoting positive organizational cultures remain key strategies for achieving effective management and the overall transformation of public senior secondary education in the state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended as follows:

- Principals should ensure that adhocracy organizational culture is maintained to enhance effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Principals should ensure that clan culture is maintained in school culture to enhance effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

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